

Studies on adsorption of carbaryl as influenced by soil organic matter (SOM) and other soil characteristics

I. Ali*, H. S. Rathore and K. K. Singh

Department of Applied Chemistry, Z. H. College of Engineering & Technology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002, India

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Adsorption of carbaryl (insecticide) has been studied on soils (untreated) and soils free of organic matter (O.M.). Freundlich and Langmuir equations are used to characterise the isotherms. Simple correlation analysis shows the significant influence of organic matter on the adsorption of carbaryl by untreated soils. In case of O.M.-free soils, adsorption is found to be correlated with the clay content and specific surface area. The clay content of the soil (O.M.-free) accounts for a very large proportion of the variation in adsorption (k value). Exothermic nature of adsorption illustrates its temperature-dependence. Evaluation of thermodynamic parameters indicates the physical nature of adsorption.

The absorption process is important in determining the fate and effectiveness of the pesticides in soil environment¹. Earlier works^{2,3} relating to adsorption of pesticides by soils and soil constituents show that the nature and extent of sorption depend upon the nature of soil constituents, pesticides and other environmental factors like temperature, soil reaction and soil moisture. The fate and behaviour of pesticides in soil are influenced by numerous interactions with soil, living and inanimate components. Adsorption appears to be one of the major factors affecting the movement of pesticides in the soil.

The purpose of the present work is to establish isotherms for adsorption of the contact insecticide carbaryl (1-naphthyl n-methylcarbamate) by specific O.M. fraction. Evaluation of the thermodynamic behavior is reported to get more comprehensive information regarding the nature of adsorption and role of soil separates on such adsorption.

Results and Discussion

The amount of carbaryl sorbed by these two soils is correlated with physicochemical characteristics of the soil (Table 1). From the percentage of mechanical separates the soils can be categorized as sandy loam.

The values of k and $1/n$ are presented in Table 2 for different adsorbate-adsorbent interactions at different temperatures. The higher adsorption by untreated B-soil is due to its higher organic matter content, and high clay con-

tent is responsible for higher retention of pesticides in comparison to the other soil. The untreated soils possess higher k values than the O.M.-free soils. The higher k values for A-soil indicate higher affinity of pesticide for mineral surfaces. Similar reports are available from earlier studies^{4,5}.

The values of $1/n$ are less than unity, and are higher for adsorption of carbaryl by O.M.-free soils than those for adsorption by untreated soils (Tables 1 and 2).

The values of k and $1/n$ decrease with decreasing percentage of organic matter in both the soils A and B, i.e. values of k and $1/n$ are higher on untreated than those on treated soil (O.M.-free soils) (Freundlich isotherm diagrams not shown). Hence, it is evident that the O.M. plays a significant role in the adsorption of carbaryl.

The changes in the standard free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) were evaluated from the adsorption data⁶ at 40, 25 and 5° (Table 3). The ΔG° values are small and negative for all the adsorbate-adsorbent interactions. It varies from -14 to -16 kJ mol⁻¹ and increases, in most cases, with decrease of temperature, indicating spontaneous nature of the adsorption processes. Similar results were reported in the earlier studies⁷. The values of ΔH° are small and negative indicating physical type of adsorption³. The values of ΔS° lie between 63.54 and 76.48 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹. Such values suggest that the adsorbate molecules are somewhat ordered on the adsorbate surface. Similar results were obtained from earlier studies^{3,5,7}. The deviations from such

Table 1. Physicochemical data of untreated and treated soils

Soil	Organic matter %	Mechanical composition %			EC _e ds m ⁻¹ at 25°	pH (1 : 2)		CEC (meq/100 g soil)		Specific surface area m ² g ⁻¹	
		Sand	Silt	Clay		Untreated	O.M.-free	Untreated	O.M.-free	Untreated	O.M.-free
A	0.6	57	30	13	0.9	8.2	7.4	6.0	7.2	76	62
B	0.7	64	21	15	1.0	8.0	8.1	7.0	6.2	87	71

Table 2. Freundlich constants (K and $1/n$) for adsorption of carbaryl on untreated and O.M.-free soils

Soil	Treatment	At 5°			At 25°			At 40°		
		$1/n$	$\log k$	k ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	$1/n$	$\log k$	k (mg g^{-1})	$1/n$	$\log k$	k (mg g^{-1})
A	Untreated	1.20	1.10	12.58	1.33	0.85	7.08	1.30	0.68	4.79
	O.M.-Free	1.15	0.75	5.62	1.20	0.67	4.68	1.25	-0.40	2.51
B	Untreated	1.30	1.01	10.23	1.35	0.83	6.80	1.25	0.60	3.98
	O.M.-Free	1.15	0.78	6.03	1.25	0.75	5.62	1.20	-0.30	2.00

Table 3. Values of thermodynamic parameters associated with adsorption of carbaryl

Soil	Treatment	Temp. °C	$10^{-2} K_0$	ΔG°	ΔH°	ΔS°
				kJ mol^{-1}	kJ mol^{-1}	JK mol^{-1}
A	Untreated	40	4.79	-16.06	3.83	63.54
		25	7.08	-16.26		
		5	12.58	-16.49		
	O.M.-Free	40	2.51	-14.37	9.57	76.48
		25	4.63	-15.15		
B	Untreated	5	5.62	-14.63	4.79	65.04
		40	3.98	-15.57		
		25	6.80	-16.16		
	O.M.-Free	5	10.23	-16.01	8.62	69.48
		40	2.00	-13.13		
		25	5.62	-15.69		
		5	6.03	-14.79		

molecular association are indicated by the positive values of ΔS° . Similar evidence was obtained from earlier studies⁶.

An attempt has also been made to examine the data obtained in the light of Langmuir equation (Langmuir isotherm diagrams not shown). Unfortunately, no proper sequence with respect to temperature has been obtained. Similar reports are available from earlier studies⁸. Thus, sorption data for carbaryl could be best fitted to a Freundlich-type equation while less closely fitted to the Langmuir equation.

Experimental

Carbaryl (97.3%, Union Carbide) and carbaryl dust (0% WDP, Bhopal Pesticides Pvt. Ltd., India) were used. A Li-10 pH meter, a CM82 conductivity bridge and a Bausch & Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer were used. All reagents and chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Aqueous solution of carbaryl: A 50% carbaryl dust (2 g) was stirred with distilled water (200 ml) for 0.5 h. The suspension was allowed to settle and the supernatant was filtered. The process was repeated twice as above with the undissolved residue. The combined filtrate was made upto 1 dm³ with distilled water and used for adsorption studies.

Properties of the soil: Soil samples (collected from two places of Aligarh district, namely, University Farm and a private farm of village Sathiya, block Sasni) were air-dried, ground to pass through 600 mesh sieve and stored in glass bottles. The physicochemical properties such as particle size, pH, EC_e, organic matter content, cation exchange capacity, and specific surface area were evaluated as per

standard procedures⁹. SOM was oxidized with H₂O₂.

Spectrophotometric determination of carbaryl:

The spectrophotometric method for carbaryl given by Yuen¹⁰ was used in the present study.

Standardization of carbaryl: To known volumes of a standard carbaryl solution (50–200 μg) were added distilled water (20 ml), and sulphanic acid (5 ml) and 16% NaOH after 10 min, and the volume was made upto 100 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of the pink colored solution was measured at 520 nm against the reagent blank. A calibration curve was made. The molar absorption coefficient was found to be 2.833×10^4 . This calibration curve was used to standardize the carbaryl which was found to be 35 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Absorption isotherms: Soil sample (1 g), aqueous solution of carbaryl (1–10 ml) and distilled water (9–10 ml) taken in boiling tubes were equilibrated for 6 h with intermittent shaking at 5, 25 and $40 \pm 1^\circ$, in a constant temperature water-bath. The blanks were also maintained simultaneously. The slurry was centrifuged at 200 rpm for 5 min and the supernatant was filtered. The color was developed as above and the absorbance was recorded at 520 nm.

Freundlich isotherm has been used to describe sorption of pesticides by soils using the formula,

$$\log X/m = \log k + 1/n \log C$$

where x/m is the pesticide sorbed ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), k the distribution coefficient and $1/n$ the slope indicating the variability in the amount of pesticide sorbed at different pesticide con-

centrations A plot of $\log (x/m)$ versus $\log C$ is a straight-line, and the constants may be evaluated from the slope $1/n$ and the intercept $\log k$. The Freundlich isotherm is purely empirical in nature.

Langmuir isotherm has also been used to describe sorption of pesticides by soils using the expression,

$$\frac{C}{x/m} = \frac{1}{kb} + \frac{1}{b} C$$

where x/m is the amount adsorbed per unit weight of adsorbent ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), C the equilibrium concentration ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), b the adsorption maximum, and k is a constant related to the bonding energy of adsorbent for adsorbate

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